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Research Article

**FREQUENCY OF PLACENTA PRAEVA AND ITS RISK
FACTORS IN PREGNANT WOMEN ATTENDING AYUB
TEACHING HOSPITAL ABBOTTABAD****¹Dr. Muhammad Rizwan Subhani, ²Muhammad Jawad, ³Dr Sunbal Naseer**
¹Ayub Medical Complex Abbottabad, ²TB Clinic Hasilpur, ³THQ Hospital Mannawa.**Article Received:** October 2019 **Accepted:** November 2019 **Published:** December 2019**Abstract:**

Background: Placenta previa is an obstetrical emergency which usually occurs in 2nd and 3rd trimester of pregnancy. In this condition the placenta lies abnormally low near the cervical os either completely or partially. It poses serious threat to maternal and foetal health. This study was carried out to find the frequency and risk factors of placenta previa in pregnant women attending the gynaecology unit in ATH.

Methods: It was a cross-sectional study carried out on pregnant women in gynaecology/obstetrics department ATH, Abbottabad from November 2018 to June 2019; all pregnant women having POG > 28 weeks were included in the study; sample size was 142 and sampling technique was non probability convenient sampling. Data was analysed using SPSS version 16.0.

Results: The frequency of placenta previa was found to be 6.3%. The mean age was 26.33 ± 5.36 years. Mean parity was 1.44 ± 1.57 and mean gravida was 2.92 ± 2.13 . Majority of women with placenta previa were in age group "below 35 years" (88.7%). 66.7% of the patients diagnosed with placenta previa had a history of previous Cesarean section (p value=0.086). 22.2% of the pregnant women with placenta previa had a history of previously diagnosed placenta previa (p value=0.047). 33.3 % of patients diagnosed with placenta previa had a history of abortion (p value=0.51). 55.6% of the patients diagnosed with placenta previa were grand multigravida followed by multigravida (44.4%) whereas there were no primigravida (p value=0.01). 77.8% of the patients diagnosed with placenta previa were multiparous followed by primiparous (22.2%), whereas there were no nulliparous women patients (p value= 0. 029).

Conclusion: The frequency of placenta previa was 6.3% which is abnormally high. Majority of the cases were in the age group of "below 35 years of age" (77.8%). History of previous placenta previa, gravida and parity were found to be major risk factors for placenta previa. History of previous caesarean section and age were also associated with placenta previa but were statistically insignificant

Keywords: Placenta previa, previous caesarean section.

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INTRODUCTION:

It is an obstetrical emergency which usually occurs in 2nd and 3rd trimester of pregnancy. In this condition the placenta lies abnormally low near the cervical os. It poses a serious threat to the health of mother as well as the baby. It is associated with an increased maternal morbidity and mortality.¹ The incidence of placenta previa has been variously reported to range from 0.1% to 0.5%.² In Pakistan the frequency of placenta previa has been reported to be in between 0.51-3.5%.³ The maternal mortality rate secondary to placenta previa is 0.03%. The incidence of placenta previa increases with previous cesarean section i.e. 1.87% with previous one cesarean section, 2.4% for two cesarean section, 2.8% for three and 10% for four or more caesarean sections.⁴ The etiology still remains controversial but the generally accepted theories revolve around endometrial and myometrial damage along with genetic abnormalities. Blastocyst completely embeds in the endometrium in a normal pregnancy, failure of proper vascularization of endometrium, delayed ovulation and previous trauma to endometrium due to any cause increases probability for placenta previa.⁵

The risk factors for placenta previa are smoking, previous cesarean sections, advanced maternal age, multiparity and conception by in IVF, previous abortion and placenta previa in a previous pregnancy.^{6,7} The usual presentation of placenta previa is painless vaginal bleeding most in late 2nd trimester or 3rd trimester. The diagnosis is confirmed through an ultrasound and sometimes is discovered incidentally in an operation.⁸ The most profound maternal risks associated with placenta previa are anesthesia and surgical complications, postpartum sepsis and placenta accrete. Placenta previa increases the risk of neonatal mortality by 3 times which is primarily due to preterm birth of the baby. Perinatal mortality is currently 4-8%, due to consequences of prematurity. Fetal and neonatal complications associated with placenta previa are congenital anomalies, respiratory distress syndrome, still birth and anemia.⁹

Availability of blood transfusion can significantly reduce the maternal morbidity and mortality as all complications are a sequel of blood loss, better NICU can reduce the perinatal mortality and morbidity. Early diagnosis by antenatal USG even before the

first episode of bleeding can be significant in deciding the fate of mother and child, once the condition is diagnosed, the case should be carefully managed and all steps required should be taken to treat the complications associated with such cases.^{10, 11} The aim of this study is to determine the incidence of placenta previa along with its risk factors in Gynecology/obstetrics unit of ATH. It can be used in future maternal and child health care policies to reduce morbidity and mortality by placenta previa through modification of modifiable risk factors and through multiple awareness programs.

STUDY METHODOLOGY:

Study Design: Cross sectional study.

Population Setting: Gynecology / Obstetrics Department ATH, Abbottabad.

Study Population: Pregnant women.

Study Duration: Eight months (November 2018 to June 2019).

Sample Size: 142

Sampling Technique: Non probability convenient sampling.

Sample Selection:

Inclusion Criteria:

1. All pregnant women having POG \geq 28 weeks were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Pregnant women unsure of dates.
2. Pregnant women diagnosed with eclampsia.

Data Collection:

Prior Permission was taken from hospital administration to conduct the research. Special care of confidentiality of women participating in the research was taken. Informed verbal consent was taken from every woman who participated in our study.

DATA ANALYSIS:

Data was analysed using SPSS version 16.0. Categorical variables like past history of cesarean section, abortion and age categories etc. were described in terms of frequencies and percentages. A p value of ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant for association between categorical variable. Quantitative variables were described in terms of Mean, Median, Mode, and Standard Deviation like age, parity, gravidity etc. Data was presented in the form of tables and figures.

RESULTS:

Figure 1: Age of Pregnant Women in Years.

It ranged from 16-40 years. Majority of the patients were aged 25 years (n=21, 14.8%). It ranged from 16-40 years. Mean age was 26.33 ± 5.368 years, median and mode were 25 years.

Figure 2: Education of Pregnant women.

Majority of the patients were uneducated (n=91, 64.1%). 35.9% (n=51) were educated.

Figure 3: Occupation of pregnant women.

95.1% (n=135) of the women were housewives where as 4.9% (n=7) were working women.

Figure 4: Residence of the pregnant women.

72.8% (n=102) of the patients belonged to rural are whereas 28.2% (n=40) belonged to urban areas.

Figure 5: Socioeconomic status of pregnant women.

66.9% (n=95) of the patients belonged to middle class whereas 33.1% (n=47) belonged to lower class.

Figure 6: Age Categories of pregnant women

88.7% (n=126) of the patients were below 35 years whereas 11.3% (n=16) were aged 35 years and above.

Figure 7: Categories of Parity among pregnant women.

Majority of women were multiparous (n=56, 39.4%) followed by nulliparous (n=51, 35.9%). 24.6% (n=35) of the women were primiparous.

Figure 8: Categories of Gravida among pregnant women.

Majority of the women were multigravida (n=72, 50.7%) followed by primigravida (n=42, 29.6%). 19.7% (n=28) of the patients were Grand multigravida.

Figure 9: History of Abortion in pregnant women.

28.9% (n=41) of the patients underwent abortion whereas 71.1% (n=101) didn't.

Figure 10: No. of Abortions Pregnant women have gone through.

71.1% (n=101) of patients didn't undergo abortion. 20.1% (n=29) of patients underwent abortion one time. 7% (n=10) underwent abortion 2 times whereas one women had abortion 3 times and other women 13 times.

Figure 11: Parity of pregnant women.

The mean parity was 1.44 ± 1.57 . The mode was 0. The minimum parity was 1 while the maximum was 16. The range of parity was 6.

Figure 12: Gravidity of pregnant women.

Mean gravida was 2.92 ± 2.135 . The mode was 1 gravida. The minimum gravida was 1 while the maximum gravida was 16. The range of gravida was 15.

Figure 13: History of smoking and snuffing in pregnant women

None of the patients had a smoking or snuffing history.

Figure 14: Period of Gestation (POG) of pregnant women.

Mean Period of gestation was 36.87 ± 3.120 weeks. Mode was 38. The minimum POG was 29 weeks while maximum POG was 42 weeks. The range of the POG was 13 weeks.

Figure 15: Status of placenta previa in pregnant women.

6.3% (n=9) of the pregnant women had placenta previa. Majority didn't have it (n=133, 93.7%).

Placenta Previa and Previous Caesarean Section of the Patient					
		Previous Caesarean Section of the Patient		Total (%)	p value
		Yes (%)	No (%)		
Status of Placenta Previa	Yes	6 (66.7)	3 (33.3)	9 (100)	0.086
	No	50 (37.6)	83 (62.4)	133 (100)	
Total		56 (39.4)	86 (60.60)	142 (100)	

Table 1: Association of Placenta Previa with Previous Caesarean Section of the Patient.

66.7% (n=6) of the patients diagnosed with placenta previa had a history of previous Cesarean section whereas 33.3% (n=3) of the patients didn't have a history of previous cesarean section. However the p value was insignificant with a value of 0.086.

Association of Placenta Previa with number of previous Caesarean Sections								
		Number of previous Caesarean Sections					Total (%)	p value
		1 (%)	2 (%)	3 (%)	4 (%)	5 (%)		
Status of Placenta Praevia	Yes	6 (100)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	6 (100)	0.611
	No	34 (68)	10 (20)	3 (6)	2 (4)	1 (1)	50 (100)	
Total		40 (71.4)	10 (17.9)	3 (5.4)	2 (3.6)	1 (1.8)	9 (100)	

Table 2: Association of Placenta Previa with number of Previous Caesarean Section(s) of the Patient.

100% (n=6) of the patients who had placenta previa and a history of previous Cesarean section underwent caesarean section only 1 time. The p value was insignificant with a value of 0.611.

Association of Placenta Praevia with Previously diagnosed Placenta Praevia of the Patient					
		Previously diagnosed Placenta Praevia of the Patient		Total (%)	p value
		Yes (%)	No (%)		
Status of Placenta Praevia	Yes	2 (22.2)	7 (77.8)	9 (100)	0.047
	No	4 (3)	129 (97)	133 (100)	
Total		6 (4.2)	136 (95.88)	142 (100)	

Table 3: Association of Placenta Previa with previously diagnosed Placenta Previa of the Patient.

22.2% of the pregnant women with placenta previa had a history of previously diagnosed placenta previa whereas 77.8% didn't have a history of placenta previa. 3% of the pregnant women who didn't have placenta previa had a previous history of placenta previa. The p value was also significant with a value of 0.047.

Association of Placenta Praevia with History of abortion					
		History of abortion		Total (%)	p value
		Yes (%)	No (%)		
Status of Placenta Praevia	Yes	3 (33.3)	6 (66.7)	9 (100)	0.51
	No	38 (28.6)	95 (71.4)	133 (100)	
Total		41 (28.9)	101 (71.1)	142 (100)	

Table 4: Association of Placenta Previa with History of Abortion of the Patient.

33.3% (n=3) of the patients diagnosed with placenta previa had a history of abortion whereas 66.7% (n=6) of the patients didn't have a history of abortion. Also 28.6% (n=38) of the patients with history of abortion didn't have placenta previa. The p value was insignificant with a value of 0.51.

Association of Placenta Previa with History of Previously Induced Abortion(s) of the Patient					
		Previously Induced Abortions of the Patient		Total (%)	p value
		Yes (%)	No (%)		
Status of Placenta Praevia	Yes	1 (11.1)	8 (88.9)	9 (100)	0.374
	No	6 (4.5)	127 (95.5)	133 (100)	
Total		7 (4.9)	135 (95.1)	142 (100)	

Table 5: Association of Placenta Previa with History of Previously Induced Abortion(s) of the Patient.

11.1% (n=1) of the patients diagnosed with placenta previa had a history of previously induce abortion whereas 88.9% (n=8) of the patients didn't have a history previously induced abortion. Also 4.5% (n=6) of the patients with history of a previously induced abortion didn't have placenta previa. The p value was insignificant with a value of 0.374.

Association of Placenta Praevia with Gravida						
		Categories of Gravida			Total (%)	p value
		Primigravida (%)	Multigravida (%)	Grand Multigravida (%)		
Status of Placenta Praevia	Yes	0 (0)	4 (44.4)	5 (55.6)	9 (100)	0.01
	No	42 (31.6)	68 (51.1)	23 (17.3)	133 (100)	
Total		42 (29.6)	72 (50.7)	28 (19.7)	142 (100)	

Table 6: Association of Placenta Previa with Gravida of the Patient.

None of the patients diagnosed with placenta previa was primigravida. 55.6% (n=5) of the patients diagnosed with placenta previa were grand multigravida whereas 44.4% (n=4) were multigravida. The p value was significant with a value of 0.01.

Association of Placenta Praevia with Parity:

		Category of Parity			Total (%)	p value
		Nulliparous (%)	Primiparous (%)	Multiparous (%)		
Status of Placenta Praevia	Yes	0 (0)	2 (22.2)	7 (77.8)	9 (100)	0.029
	No	51 (38.3)	33 (24.8)	49 (36.8)	133 (100)	
Total		51 (35.9)	35 (24.6)	56 (39.4)	142 (100)	

Table 7: Association of Placenta Previa with Parity of the Patient.

None of the patients diagnosed with placenta previa was nulliparous. 77.8% (n=7) of the patients diagnosed with placenta previa were multiparous whereas 22.2% (n=2) were primiparous. The p value was also significant with a value of 0.029.

Association of Placenta Praevia with Age					
		Age categories		Total (%)	p value
		35 years & above (%)	Below 35 years (%)		
Status of Placenta Praevia	Yes	2 (22.2)	7 (77.8)	9 (100)	0.268
	No	14 (10.5)	119 (89.5)	133 (100)	
Total		16 (11.3)	126 (88.7)	142 (100)	

Table 8: Association of Placenta Previa with Previous Caesarean Section of the Patient.

77.8% (n=7) of the patients who had placenta previa were in “below 35 years of age” group whereas 22.2% (n=2) of the patients were in “35 years and above age” group. However the p value was insignificant with a value of 0.268.

DISCUSSION:

The frequency of placenta previa was found to be 6.3% which is higher as compared to other studies conducted previously, in Nigeria it was found to be 2%, in Tanzania it was 0.6% and in Iran 0.7%.^{2,8,22} This could be due to different demographic factors or due to small sample size. Mean age was found to be 26.33 ± 5.368 years. 77.8% of the patients who had placenta previa were in “below 35 years of age” group, this is comparable to several studies conducted before, in which it was found to be 62.5% and 52% respectively, however the association was insignificant in our study (p value=0.286).^{9,18}.

In our study 66.7% of the patients diagnosed with placenta previa had history of previous Cesarean section, this is in conjunction with previous studies in which it was found to be 56.5%, 58.1% and 61.7% respectively.^{7,18,22} However the association was statistically insignificant in our study (p value=0.086). All of the patients (100%) who were diagnosed with placenta previa and had history of previous Cesarean section underwent caesarean section only 1 time. This in contrast to a previous study conducted in Pakistan in which majority of the patients underwent caesarean section 3 times (37.7%) and 23.3% underwent caesarean section one time.¹ Besides, according to our results the association was found to be statistically insignificant (p value=0.611). In our study 22.2% of the pregnant women with placenta previa had a history of previously diagnosed placenta previa, this is in approximate conjunction with a study conducted in KSA in which it was found to be 26.1%.¹⁸ 3% of the pregnant women who didn't have placenta previa had a previous history of placenta previa which is less as compared to 22.2% in women diagnosed with placenta previa. The p value was also significant with a value of 0.047, hence history of previous placenta previa can be regarded as a risk factor for placenta previa.

33.3 % of patients diagnosed with placenta previa had history of abortion which is higher as compared to those who didn't have placenta previa (28.6%), however there isn't a marked difference between the two. In a study conducted in Croatia it was found to be 45.5% in patients with placenta previa and 23% who didn't have placenta previa.¹⁷ Also, our association is found to be statistically insignificant (p value=0.51).

11.1% of the patients diagnosed with placenta previa had a history of previously induced abortion, this in contrast to a study conducted previously in Malaysia in which it was found to be 31.4%.¹³ The association was statistically insignificant (p value=0.374). Majority of the patients (55.6%) diagnosed with placenta previa were grand multigravida followed by multigravida (44.4%), however there were no primigravida. This is comparable to a study conducted in Pakistan in which majority of the patients were grand multigravida (58.7%) followed by multigravida (36.8), and no primigravida (0%).¹ The association was found to be statistically significant (p value=0.01). Hence gravida of patient can be regarded as an important risk factor for placenta previa. According to our study majority of the patients (77.8%) diagnosed with placenta previa were multiparous followed by primiparous (22.2%), whereas there were no nulliparous women with placenta previa. This is in conjunction to several studies conducted internationally in which the frequency of placenta previa increases with increasing parity.^{4,7,8,11,17,18,25} Our results were statistically significant with a p value of 0.029. Thus parity of patient can be regarded as a risk factor for placenta previa. None of the patients in our study had a smoking history which is contradictory to study conducted in Croatia where several women had history of smoking.¹⁷ This could be attributed to social and religious factors in our community.

CONCLUSION:

The frequency of placenta previa was 6.3% which is abnormally high. Majority of the cases were in the age group of “below 35 years of age” (77.8%). History of previous placenta previa, gravida and parity were found to be major risk factors for placenta previa. History of previous cesarean section and age were also associated with placenta previa but were statistically insignificant.

Limitations:

1. Small sample size.
2. Nonprobability convenient sampling technique.
3. Home deliveries, with only reporting to hospital for complication.

Recommendations:

1. Improved MCHC with proper awareness among women of the region.
2. Promote family planning.
3. Proper database of women storing all information such as history of previous abortions, previous C-section, previous placenta previa etc.

4. Counselling mothers with more than one risk factor for placenta previa.

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Appendix:

Research proforma

This researched titled “**Frequency of Placenta Previa and its Risk Factors in patients of**

Gynae. & Obs. Department MTI-ATH Abbottabad” It is assured that your information regarding this questionnaire will remain strictly confidential and will only be used for research purpose.

1.MR# _____ 2.Age: _____ 3. Education _____

4	Occupation	Working woman	Housewife	5	Residence	Urban	Rural
		Socioeconomic Status				Lower Class	Middle Class

7.Address _____

8.POG ____ Weeks Gravida _____ Para _____ Abortions _____ Alive _____

1	Diagnosis?	Normal Placenta	Placenta Praevia	Any Other _____?
2	Have you delivered through a Cesarean Section in the past?			Yes No
3	If Yes, how many times you have delivered through a Cesarean Section?			_____times.
4	Have you been previously diagnosed with Placenta Praevia?			Yes No
5	Have you been through an induced abortion in the past?			Yes No

6	Have you gone for any uterine surgery other than Cesarean Section in the past?	Yes	No
7	If Yes, please specify.	_____	
8	Have you used any assisted reproductive technique other than fertility pills?	Yes	No
9	Have you been diagnosed with multiple pregnancy i.e. twins or more in current pregnancy?	Yes	No
10	Do you have any history of uterine diseases (endometriosis, fibroids or leiomyoma) other than childbirth complications?	Yes	No
11	Do you do smoke or have such history during pregnancy?	Yes	No
12	Do you use snuff (Naswar) or have such history pregnancy?	Yes	No